

CREATING 21st CENTURY INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERS: EXPLORING THE LEVEL OF MANAGEMENT SKILLS OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS

RONALIE DIANE C. ROSCO¹

ELSA C. CALLO, Ed.D²

ronaliediane.rosco@deped.gov.ph¹

elsa.callo@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0002-0224-5576¹

0000-0003-0785-4730²

Malinta Elementary School¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to analyze the 21st-century instructional leadership styles and explored the level of school principals' management skills. The respondents were 330 teachers from different public elementary schools in the District of Los Baños, Division of Laguna. The study used the descriptive-correlational design to determine if instructional leadership styles singly or in combination affect the school principal's management skills. The questionnaire in google form was used as the data gathering instrument. Data were analyzed using frequency, percent, mean, standard deviation, Pearson product-moment of correlation, multiple linear regression, and analysis of variance. The salient findings of the study are summarized as follows: Teachers perceived transformational, transactional instructional leadership styles the principals' management skills as very highly observed. The test of correlations between 21st-century instructional leadership style and level of management skills were found to be highly significant at $p < .05$ level. Transformational leadership style significantly affects school principals' management skills, while transactional leadership significantly affects human resource management and development, and school leadership and management. There were significant differences in the perceptions among respondents by schools. The study recommends that school principals may attempt to keep a high level of professional spirit and a good moral standard by adopting their management styles to sustain a good working environment for teachers and other staff in their schools.

Keywords: transformational leadership, transactional leadership, management skills, school principals, 21st-century instructional leaders